

Socio-demographic Factors, Emotional Intelligence and Childhood Adversity: Insights from In-School Adolescents in Lagos State

Taiye Emmanuel Ojo

Faculty of Social Sciences, Department of Psychology, Lagos State University, Nigeria

Abstract

Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACEs) are potentially stressful childhood events that frequently have detrimental long-term effects on a person's physical and emotional well-being. Hence, this study aims to examine the relationship between socio-demographic factors, emotional intelligence and adverse childhood experiences among in-school adolescents in Lagos State. A cross-sectional research design was employed to select 1,728 participants [males (49.5%) and females (50.5%) with a mean age = 14.73, SD = 1.66]. The participants were selected from private and public schools across four education districts in Lagos State. Four hypotheses were stated and tested using Pearson's r correlation and t-test for independent means. The results revealed that there was a significant negative relationship between emotional intelligence and adverse childhood experiences. It was further shown that male students were more prone to adverse childhood experiences compared to their female counterparts, and adolescents from a polygamous family were more exposed to adverse childhood experiences compared to adolescents from a monogamous family. Adolescents who live with both parents experienced less childhood adversity compared to adolescents who lived with father only, mother only, relatives and non-relatives. It was concluded that by nurturing emotional competence, educators and policymakers can help adolescents transform early adversity into strength, fostering healthier emotional adjustment and long-term well-being.

Keywords: *Adverse Childhood Experience, Emotional Intelligence, Family size, family structure and In-school Adolescents.*

Suggested citation: Ojo, T.E. (2025). Socio-demographic Factors, Emotional Intelligence and Childhood Adversity: Insights from In-School Adolescents in Lagos State. *European Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(6), 94-104. DOI: 10.59324/ejahss.2025.2(6).11

Introduction

Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACEs) are hypothetically stressful childhood events that frequently have detrimental long-term effects on a person's physical and emotional well-being. Adolescents' psychological and behavioural issues are mostly caused by these events, which include abuse, neglect, and dysfunctional households. The World Health Organisation states that childhood trauma, including exposure to violence, might increase an adolescent's susceptibility to mental health problems (WHO, 2020). According to some studies, traumatic childhood experiences—particularly those that originate in the child's immediate surroundings – significantly raise the likelihood that the child will experience psychological and behavioural problems in the future. (Downey & Crummy, 2022; Maurya & Maurya, 2023) Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACEs) are a broad term for these traumatic events. ACEs are situations or occurrences that lead to stress and have a long life influence on the physical and mental health and wellbeing of adolescents. Adolescence, maturity, or later life phases are frequently when the impacts of ACEs appear (O'Neil et al., 2023). Living in abusive homes, being exposed to parental substance misuse or criminal activity, experiencing physical, emotional, or sexual violence, neglect by caregivers or the environment, and sharing a home with a caregiver who has a mental illness are all

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/). The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

common instances of ACEs (O'Neil et al., 2023). Adolescents frequently encounter these negative experiences, which can have long-lasting consequences that extend into adulthood (Crouch et al., 2019).

ACEs can take many different forms, such as physical abuse, which includes pushing, slapping, or throwing things at a children; emotional abuse, which includes insults or profanity; and sexual abuse, which includes unwanted contact by an older person. Neglect is another type of ACE; it can be emotional (such as feeling unwelcome by parents) or physical (such as not having access to necessities like clothes and school materials). ACEs also include witnessing domestic violence, having a household member incarcerated, living with a family member who misuse drugs or alcohol, and going through parental separation or divorce.

A study conducted in August 2021 using data from the 2017 Behavioural Risk Factor Surveillance System (BRFSS) found that one in six persons had experienced four or more ACE categories (Greiner et al., 2021). The information also revealed that there was a connection between ACEs and causes of mortality. Research indicates that millions of children worldwide are exposed to ACEs each year (Asmussen et al., 2020), resulting in toxic stress that can change how the brain develops and affect how the body reacts to stressors in the future. According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC, 2019), ACEs are becoming a more significant public health issue since they are associated with mental illness, drug abuse, and chronic health issues in adulthood. ACEs have traditionally been divided into three main categories: family or household difficulties, abuse, and neglect (Felitti et al., 1998).

Higher ACE scores have been linked to an increase in health and disability diagnoses in recent research, highlighting the significant negative effects of childhood adversity on development and health. As ACE research has progressed, it has become evident that these events impact adolescents' neurological, socio-emotional, and behavioral development, making them a serious public health concern as well as a social one (Salawu & Owoaje, 2020). With major ramifications for both physical and mental health, the link between ACEs and risky behaviors and poor adult health outcomes is well-established (Agbaje et al., 2021).

Approximately two-thirds of Americans report having encountered one or more ACEs, demonstrating how common ACEs are in the country (Balglivio et al., 2014; Carlson et al., 2020; Merrick et al., 2018). This cumulative exposure is particularly dangerous given the evidence of a dose-response relationship wherein more exposure to a wider variety of ACEs results in even poorer outcomes (Merrick et al., 2017; Waehrer et al., 2020). While the prevalence of some ACEs, such as child abuse and neglect, has declined in the 21st century, other risky exposures, such as parental drug and alcohol use, have increased, necessitating a greater understanding of the detrimental effects of ACEs (Finkelhor et al., 2020).

Agbaje et al. (2021) used a sample from Nigeria and found that 86.7% of the sample had encountered an ACE, with 14.8% reporting one ACE, 30.5% reporting two or three ACEs, and 41.3% reporting more than four ACEs. The prevalence of adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) among these adolescents was 92.5%, according to Ojo et al. (2025); 3.1% of the adolescents reported severe ACEs, whereas 38.8% and 50.6% reported moderate and severe ACEs, respectively. 32.6% reported sexual abuse, 86.9% reported mental abuse, and 42.8% reported physical abuse. Neglect, both physical and emotional, was prevalent in 90.5% of cases. The psychological effects of ACEs on a child's developing brain are profound. Continuous exposure to these difficulties may affect people's perceptions of the world, sometimes in a hostile or skeptical way. Nearly half (46.3%) of all children and 55.7% of adolescents aged 12 to 17 in the United States had suffered at least one abuse or neglect-related ACE, according to data from the 2016 National Survey of Children's Health (NSCH) (Bethell et al., 2016). Black children (63.7%) and Hispanic/Latinx children (51.4%) had greater rates than White children (40.9%) and Asian children 23%; 10% of children nationwide have gone through three or more ACEs (Sacks & Murphy, 2018).

It has been demonstrated that various risk factor types and combinations are linked to one or more ACEs (Thornberry et al., 2014; Soares et al., 2016). Socio-demographic factors such as individual, parental history, family environment, and socioeconomic setting are some of the areas in which these variables are found (Thornberry et al., 2014; Soares et al., 2016). The probability of encountering ACEs rises with

the amount of risk variables present (Thornberry et al., 2014; Soares et al., 2016). According to Soares et al. (2016), there is a high correlation between the incidence of ACEs and a number of socioeconomic, demographic, and family-related factors, including sex, low family income, low maternal education, the absence of a mother's partner, maternal smoking, and poor maternal mental health. When studying ACEs, one of the most important demographic elements to take into account is sex-specific differences. For instance, women are more likely than males to report greater rates of ACEs (Petrucci et al., 2019). According to Soares et al. (2016), women experience ACEs more frequently than men. In a German Longitudinal research, Supke et al. (2025) examined data on ACEs from 316 households and discovered that mothers and daughters reported much more ACEs than father and sons, especially in the areas of abuse and neglect.

According to a research by Häuser et al. (2011), female sex is a predictor of both experience and severe kinds of sexual abuse. Women in the general population appear to be more vulnerable to emotional and sexual abuse than men, according to a different research by Witt et al. (2017). Research on sex differences in ACEs is limited in Nigeria (Agbaje et al., 2021; Ojo et al., 2025) For instance, Ojo et al. (2025) identified no significant differences between males and females in the examination of ACEs among teenagers, but Agbeje et al. (2021) asserted that girls reported more ACEs than boys. Most of the studies show sex differences in the connections between ACEs and health outcomes or risk behaviours; hence, taking sex-specific factors into account is essential.

Additionally, results from previous research showed that other sociodemographic characteristics, such the size of the family and being a single parent, were risk factors for child abuse (Sidebotham et al., 2001; Sidebotham et al., 2006; Stith et al., 2009). According to Sidebotham et al. (2001), this relationship may indicate a lack of resources to address the child's needs or a lack of understanding or appreciation of those requirements. Amone-P'Olak (2022) reported that family structure plays a crucial role in children's exposure to adversity. Also, Lombardi et al. (2022) claimed that children with higher ACE scores were significantly less likely to receive family-centred care. At the same time, other factors such as race/ethnicity, insurance type, home language, and lack of a regular healthcare provider were also linked to lower FCC quality. Balistreri and Alvira-Hammond (2016) in their study found that adolescents with higher ACE scores reported poorer physical health and lower emotional well-being, even after controlling for demographic and socioeconomic factors. However, the study also found that strong family functioning significantly buffered or reduced the negative effects of ACEs on adolescent outcomes. In other words, supportive and well-functioning family environments helped mitigate the harmful consequences of early life adversity.

Adversity and a lack of protective factors from an early age have been shown to increase the likelihood of long-term bad mental health concerns (Crouch et al., 2018). The relationship between emotional intelligence and better mental health has been the subject of innumerable studies. Delhom et al. (2020) looked at the relationship between emotional intelligence and coping skills and depression. The study's findings showed that people with high emotional intelligence had fewer depression symptoms because they were able to better control their emotions and employ problem-focused coping strategies (Delhom et al., 2020). A significant negative correlation was discovered between emotional intelligence and adverse childhood experiences in a study by Priyam and Nath (2021) In a different study, Ugwu et al. (2024) found that, for adolescents with low emotional intelligence, sexual and emotional abuse was positively associated with conduct issues, but not for those with moderate or high emotional intelligence. They came to the conclusion that having more emotional intelligence helps adolescents cope with ACEs more effectively and lowers their likelihood of developing behavioural issues in school (Ugwu et al., 2024). Similarly, Irshad and Lone (2025) found that there is a correlation between emotional intelligence and ACEs.

Research has long demonstrated that early childhood trauma can result in emotional and behavioural challenges, but less is known about how adolescents' emotional intelligence influences these events in Nigeria. The majority of research conducted in sub-Saharan Africa has focused on the outward manifestations of adversity, like poor academic performance, aggression, or mental health issues, while

paying less attention to the more subtle, inward-facing abilities that aid adolescents in comprehending and controlling their emotions. Many teenagers grow up under constant stress in Lagos State, where social pressure, family strife, and economic uncertainty are commonplace aspects of daily life. Despite these difficulties, some young people exhibit remarkable emotional maturity, they remain composed, empathetic, and self-controlled even under trying conditions. It's still unclear why some teenagers are able to control their emotions so well while others find it difficult. Therefore, this study aims to investigate the

relationship between emotional intelligence and adverse childhood experiences among in-school adolescents in Lagos State.

Hypothesis

1. Emotional intelligence will significantly and negatively correlate with adverse childhood experiences.
2. There will be a significant difference between sex and adverse childhood experiences
3. Family type will significantly influence adverse childhood experiences.
4. Family structure will significantly influence adverse childhood experiences

Material and Methods

Design

The study used quantitative techniques and a cross-sectional research design.

Participants and Sampling Techniques

A general power analysis (G*power) was used to determine a sample size of 1728 [males = 856 (49.5%) and females 872 (50.5%) with mean age = 14.73, SD = 1.66]. Adolescents enrolled in secondary schools in Lagos State were chosen using a four-stage multi-stage sampling technique.

Data Collection Procedures

For appropriate permission to conduct the research, an introduction letter was obtained from the researcher's institution and sent to the Head of Service, Lagos State, and the Ministry of Basic and Secondary Education, Lagos State, along with the application letter, proposal, and questionnaire. Following approval, the researcher went to the principals of the chosen schools to ask for their consent to give out questionnaires to the children. The school officials were informed of the purpose and objectives of the study. The researcher was permitted by the school administration to distribute the questionnaire among the students. Following their attendance in their respective classrooms, the chosen pupils were given consent and assent documents to take home to their parents and guardians.

The students were given surveys to complete once the parental approval forms were signed. The researchers visited each classroom and distributed the questionnaire to students who volunteered and consented to participate. The researcher built a good relationship with the participants and assured them of the study's anonymity while outlining its purpose. As the researchers awaited their pickup, the volunteers immediately completed the surveys.

Measures

A socio-demographic questionnaire was administered to the respondents to gather their sex, age and school type. Thereafter, the Redeemer's University Adverse Childhood Experiences Scale (RUACES) developed by Ojo et al. (2024), a self-developed and validated scale, was used to measure previous and ongoing adverse experiences of adolescents. The RUACES is a 21-item scale rated in a five-point Likert scale from Never (0), Rarely (1), Sometimes (2), Often (3), and Always (4).

The internal consistency of the scale was .867 (Ojo et al., 2024). Also, all the items assessing RUACES .861 and .874 indicate that the items have very good discrimination. The scoring indicates that the higher the score, the higher the exposure to adverse childhood experiences (Minimum = 0, maximum = 84). The Schutte Self-Report Emotional Intelligence Test (SSEIT): The SSEIT Emotional Intelligence Scale was developed by Schette et al. (1998). The scale consists of 33 items, each rated on a five-point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree=1 to strongly agree=5 and aiming to assess emotional intelligence based on the Mayer-Salovey-Caruso model. The scale items are designed to assess the appraisal and expression of emotion in self and others, the regulation of emotion in self and others and the utilisation of emotion in solving problems (Schette et al., 1998). A test-retest reliability study yielded a coefficient of 0.78, suggesting that the SSEIT is reliable. The pilot study conducted by the researcher reported a Cronbach's alpha reliability of 0.82. In scoring the scale, items 5, 28 and 33 should be first reversed, and after scoring all the items, all 33 items were summed to get the composite score (Minimum = 33, maximum = 165). Schuette et al. (Schette et al., 1998) reported means of 135 and 120 for therapists and prisoners, respectively and means of 131 and 125 for female and male, respectively.

Results

Hypothesis One

The result of the Pearson r showed that there was significant negative relationship between emotional intelligence and adverse childhood experiences ($r(1726) = -.187, P < .05$). The result indicates that the higher the emotional intelligence of an adolescents the lower the adverse childhood experiences and likewise the higher the adverse childhood experience, the lower the emotional intelligence among in-school adolescents in Lagos State.

Table 1. Summary of Correlation Showing the Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Adverse Childhood Experiences among In-School Adolescents in Lagos State

Variables	Mean	SD	1	2
Emotional Intelligence	132.18	18.86	-	
Adverse Childhood Experiences	19.78	15.01	-.187	-

Hypothesis Two

The result of the t-test in (Table 2) showed that sex has a significant difference in adverse childhood experiences ($t= 3.79; df(1726); P < .01$). Male in-school adolescent significantly scores higher on the measures of adverse childhood experiences than female in-school adolescents.

Table 2. Summary Table of T-Test Showing the Influence of Sex on Adverse Childhood Experiences

	Sex	Number	X	S.D	df	t	Sig
Adverse Childhood Experiences	Male	856	21.15	15.71	1726	3.79	.000
	Female	872	18.43	14.17			

Hypothesis Three

The result of the t-test in (Table 3) showed that there is a family types have significant difference on adverse childhood experiences ($t= -2.39; df(1726); P < .01$). Adolescent from a polygamous family type significantly scored higher (Mean=21.67 and SD=16.64) on the measures of adverse childhood experiences compared who came from monogamous family type (Mean=19.32 and SD=14.55).

Table 3. Summary Table of T-Test Showing the Influence of Family Types on Adverse Childhood Experiences

	Family Types	Number	X	S.D	df	T	Sig
Adverse Childhood Experiences	Monogamous	1389	19.32	14.55	1726	-2.39	.009
	Polygamous	339	21.67	16.64			

Hypothesis Four

It could be revealed from the ANOVA table that family structure has a significant influence on adolescents' exposure to Adverse Childhood Experiences [$F(4, 1723) = 9.00, p < .001$]. The Post hoc result revealed that ACEs were higher among adolescents who live with a non-relative ($M=26.01$).

Table 4. Summary Table of One-Way ANOVA Showing the Influence of Family Structure on Adverse Childhood Experiences

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	7964.166	4	1991.041	9.002	.000
Within Groups	381103.697	1723	221.186		
Total	389067.862	1727			

Table 5. Summary Table of Post Hoc Test (Scheffe) Showing Group Mean (Homogeneous Subsets)

Family Structure	N	Mean
Both parents	1199	18.4696
Relative	86	20.2860
Mother alone	243	22.3263
Father alone	144	23.6273
Non-relative	56	26.0141

Discussion

The study examined how socio-demographic factors and emotional intelligence operates as a correlates of childhood adversity among in-school adolescents in Lagos State and in the light of this, a significant relationship between emotional intelligence and adverse childhood experiences was explored and it was established that there was a significant negative correlation between emotional intelligence and adverse childhood experiences among in-school adolescents in Lagos State, signifying that the emotional functioning of adolescents is meaningfully shaped by the nature and intensity of their early life experiences either positively or negatively. The significant relationship between emotional intelligence and ACEs aligned with previous studies that early adversities can have a lifelong effect on the development of emotional intelligence (Priyam & Nath, 2021; Ugwu et al., 2024; Irshad & Lone, 2025). The development of emotional intelligence heavily depends on the quality of the care received during childhood and the friendly environmental exposure experienced by adolescents during their formative years. Adolescents who are exposed to parental neglect, abuse of any type and household/family dysfunction are predisposed to have a disrupted emotional learning process, which may weaken their ability to recognise, understand and manage emotions adaptively. Relating this to Nigerian culture, where political, social and economic volatility often interact with family-related stressors, which may silence the association between emotional intelligence and ACEs. Most adolescents navigate through complicated emotional terrains marked by conflict from parents, hardship and exposure to societal violence. The unpalatable experience could both hinder emotional intelligence and ACEs, in certain cases, strengthen emotional adaptability depending on the available support received and coping skills. Thus, the significant connection observed from this study may reflect both detrimental and compensatory effects of adversity on the development of emotional intelligence. Adolescents who have endured mild to moderate

adversity may develop stronger emotional control and empathy as survival mechanisms, while those who have faced chronic or severe trauma may exhibit diminished emotional regulation capacities.

The findings found a significant difference between sex and adverse childhood experiences, which agrees with several findings (Agbaje et al. 2021; Soares et al., 2016; Haahr-Pedersen et al. 2020), Häuser et al. (2011) but disagrees in that most of the findings reported that females are more exposed to ACEs compared to males Agbaje et al. (2021), Soares et al. (2016), Haahr-Pedersen et al. (2020) and Häuser et al. (2011). However, the finding disagree totally with the finding of Ojo et al (2025) that no significant differences were found between male and female on adverse childhood experiences.

The finding implies that the cultural expectations around masculinity in many parts of Nigeria encourage boys to display toughness, independence, and emotional restraint, which can inadvertently place them in environments that normalise aggression or emotional neglect. As a result, male adolescents may internalise or underreport emotional distress, making their exposure to ACEs both more frequent and less visibly acknowledged. Female adolescents, on the other hand, though not immune to adversity, may benefit from relatively stronger emotional socialisation within family systems, where they are often encouraged to express emotions, seek support, and maintain close social bonds. These relational dynamics might buffer them, to some extent, from the full psychological impact of adverse experiences

Furthermore, a significant relationship was established between family type and adverse childhood experiences, with adolescents from a polygamous family experiencing higher adversity compared to adolescents from a monogamous family. This suggests that family instability, emotional inconsistency and increased interpersonal conflict in polygamous families may contribute to an increased risk of exposure to domestic or household adversity. Furthermore, polygamous families are often exposed to rivalry from siblings, limited and unequal distribution of resources and conflicts between/among parents, which may increase exposure to stress and adversity in children. This finding is consistent with Balisteri and Alvir (2016), who found that family functions moderate the relationship between ACEs and adolescent health with well-functioning families helping to reduce the negative effects of childhood adversity. Also, Amone-P'Olak (2022) found a significant difference between family type and Aces. Furthermore, Shaiful et al. 2021 findings complement this finding in that their study revealed that children from polygamous families had higher levels of psychological impacts than those from monogamous families, This suggest that polygamy effects on children are more noticeable and could expose them to adversity and could potential affect their academic achievement, interpersonal relationship, emotion regulations, and later life development in adulthood (Al-Krenawi & Lightman, 2000; Elbedour et al., 2003)

Finally, family structure, such as who the adolescents live with, was found to significantly influence adverse childhood experiences among in-school adolescents, such that adolescents who live with both parents experienced less childhood adversity compared to adolescents who lived with father only, mother only, relatives and non-relatives. This indicates that a stable family structure where both parents live together to raise their offspring provides a protective buffer for adolescents against any exposure to adversity compared to adolescents living with a non-relatives who experienced a higher levels of adversity. This shows the essentiality in family structure and constant caregiving in shaping emotional security in adolescents. The finding align with a prominent Ecological theory of Urie Bronfenbrenner (1979), which emphasised that the family is an important microsystem that influences children's developmental outcomes. Likewise, the finding support the theoretical underpinning of Bowlby Attachment Theory (1988) which centred on the premise that secure and nurturing caregiver relationships, such as parents protect children from emotional distress that may stem from the environment and the exposure to developmental vulnerability. The study further agrees with previous findings by (Soares et al., 2016) who found an association between family-related factors such as maternal or paternal partners and the incidence of ACEs. Similary, Lombardi et (2022) found that childhood adversities are lesser in children who received family-centred care compare to children who didn't receive family-centred care. Also, the finding is consistent with the study of Amone-P'Olak (2022), who found that single-mother and separated/divorced families had significantly higher rates of ACEs compared to those from nuclear

families. Specifically, the attributable risk of experiencing ACEs was between 2.85 and 4.13 times higher for those from single-mother families, and between 3.69 and 6.32 times higher for those from separated/divorced families. This showed that family structure plays a crucial role in children's exposure to adversity.

Conclusion

This study sheds light on how emotional intelligence operates as a correlate of childhood adversity among in-school adolescents in Lagos State. The findings reveal that adverse childhood experiences significantly shape adolescents' emotional functioning, influencing their ability to perceive, understand, and regulate emotions. Yet, even within contexts of hardship, many adolescents demonstrate adaptive emotional capacities, highlighting the potential of emotional intelligence as a pathway to resilience. The observed gender differences, with male adolescents reporting higher exposure to adversity, further emphasise the influence of sociocultural and environmental factors on developmental outcomes. These insights emphasise the need for gender-sensitive, trauma-informed, and emotionally focused interventions within Nigerian schools. By nurturing emotional competence, educators and policymakers can help adolescents transform early adversity into strength, fostering healthier emotional adjustment and long-term well-being.

Notwithstanding its significant contributions, this study has drawbacks. The use of self-report surveys, which might incorporate biases including social desirability, inaccurate recollection, and participant-subjective item interpretation, is one of the main weaknesses. The participants' emotional states or their ideas of what is socially acceptable may have affected their responses, even if the instruments used were standardised and validated. The cross-sectional aspect of the study's predictive analysis is another drawback, since it limits the capacity to make causal conclusions on the connection between ACEs and emotional intelligence. Moreover, Lagos State was the study's geographic focus, which may not accurately represent the sociocultural realities or behavioural patterns of adolescents in Nigeria's rural or less urbanised areas, despite its diversity and population.

References

- Agbaje, O. S., Nnaji, C. P., Nwagu, E. N., Iweama, C. N., Umoke, P. C. I., Ozoemena, L. E., & Abba, C. C. (2021). Adverse childhood experiences and psychological distress among higher education students in Southeast Nigeria: An institutional-based cross-sectional study. *Archives of Public Health*, 79(1), 62. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13690-021-00587-3>
- Al-Krenawi, A., & Lightman, E. S. (2000). Learning achievement, social adjustment, and family conflict among Bedouin-Arab children from polygamous and monogamous families. *Journal of Social Psychology*, 140(3), 345–355. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00224540009600475>
- Amone-P'Olak, K. (2022). Prevalence, distribution, and attributable risks of adverse childhood experiences in different family types: A survey of young adults in Botswana. *Child Abuse & Neglect*, 126, 105513. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chiabu.2022.105513>
- Asmussen, K., Fischer, F., Drayton, E., & McBride, T. (2020). *Adverse childhood experiences: What we know, what we don't know, and what should happen next*. Early Intervention Foundation.
- Balistreri, K. S., & Alvira-Hammond, M. (2016). Adverse childhood experiences, family functioning, and adolescent health and emotional well-being. *Public Health*, 132, 72–78. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.puhe.2015.10.034>
- Bethell, C., Gombojav, N., Solloway, M., & Wissow, L. (2016). Adverse childhood experiences, resilience and mindfulness-based approaches: Common denominator issues for children with emotional, mental, or behavioural problems. *Child and Adolescent Psychiatric Clinics of North America*, 25(2), 139–156.

- Bowlby, J. (1988). *A secure base: Parent-child attachment and healthy human development*. New York, NY: Basic Books.
- Bronfenbrenner, U. (1979). *The ecology of human development: Experiments by nature and design*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Carlson, J. S., Yohannan, J., Darr, C. L., Turley, M. R., Larez, N. A., & Perfect, M. M. (2020). Prevalence of adverse childhood experiences in school-aged youth: A systematic review (1990–2015). *International Journal of School & Educational Psychology*, 8(Suppl 1), 2–23. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21683603.2018.1548397>
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. (2019). *Adverse childhood experiences (ACEs): Preventing early trauma to improve adult health*. Vital Signs.
- Crouch, E., Probst, J. C., Radcliff, E., Bennett, K. J., & McKinney, S. H. (2019). Prevalence of adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) among US children. *Child Abuse & Neglect*, 92, 209–218. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chiabu.2019.04.010>
- Crouch, E., Radcliff, E., Stropolis, M., & Srivasta, A. (2018). Safe, stable, and nurtured: Protective factors against poor physical and mental health outcomes following exposure to adverse childhood experiences (ACEs). *Journal of Child & Adolescent Trauma*, 12, 165–173. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40653-018-0217-9>
- Delhom, I., Satorres, E., & Meléndez, J. C. (2020). Can we improve skills in older adults? Emotional intelligence, life satisfaction, and resilience. *Psychosocial Intervention*, 29(3), 133–139. <https://doi.org/10.5093/pi2020a8>
- Downey, C., & Crummy, A. (2022). The impact of childhood trauma on children's wellbeing and adult behavior. *European Journal of Trauma & Dissociation*, 6(1), 100237. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejtd.2021.100237>
- Elbedour, S., Bart, W. M., & Hektner, J. (2003). Intelligence and family marital structure: The case of adolescents from monogamous and polygamous families among Bedouin Arabs in Israel. *Journal of Social Psychology*, 143(1), 95–110.
- Felitti, V. J., Anda, R. F., Nordenberg, D., Williamson, D. F., Spitz, A. M., Edwards, V., Koss, M. P., & Marks, J. S. (1998). Relationship of childhood abuse and household dysfunction to many of the leading causes of death in adults: The ACE study. *American Journal of Preventive Medicine*, 14(8), 245–258. (DOI не найден)
- Finkelhor, D. (2020). Trends in adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) in the United States. *Child Abuse & Neglect*, 108, 104641.
- Greiner, B., Checketts, J., Fishbeck, K., & Hartwell, M. (2021). Clinical characteristics and lifestyle behaviors among individuals with arthritis: An analysis of 2017 Behavioral Risk Factor Surveillance System data. *Journal of Osteopathic Medicine*, 121(1), 113–119.
- Haahr-Pedersen, I., Perera, C., Hyland, P., Vallières, F., Murphy, D., Hansen, M., Spitz, P., Hansen, P., & Cloitre, M. (2020). Females have more complex patterns of childhood adversity: Implications for mental, social, and emotional outcomes in adulthood. *European Journal of Psychotraumatology*, 11(1), 1708618. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20008198.2019.1708618>
- Häuser, W., Schmutzer, G., Brähler, E., & Glaesmer, H. (2011). Maltreatment in childhood and adolescence: Results from a survey of a representative sample of the German population. *Deutsches Ärzteblatt International*, 108(17), 287–294. <https://doi.org/10.3238/arztebl.2011.0287>
- Irshad, S., & Lone, A. (2025). Adverse childhood experiences and their influence on psychological well-being and emotional intelligence among university students. *BMC Psychology*, 13(1), 255. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40359-025-02565-8>

- Lombardi, B. M., Zerden, L. d., Lee, H., & Moehling Geffel, K. (2022). Do families exposed to adverse childhood experiences report family-centered care? *Societies*, 12, 168. <https://doi.org/10.3390/soc12060168>
- Maurya, C., & Maurya, P. (2023). Adverse childhood experiences and health risk behaviours among adolescents and young adults: Evidence from India. *BMC Public Health*, 23(1), 536.
- Merrick, M. T., Ford, D. C., Ports, K. A., & Guinn, A. S. (2018). Prevalence of adverse childhood experiences from the 2011–2014 Behavioral Risk Factor Surveillance System in 23 states. *JAMA Pediatrics*, 172, 1038–1044.
- Merrick, M. T., Ports, K. A., Ford, D. C., Afifi, T. O., Gershoff, E. T., & Grogan-Kaylor, A. (2017). Unpacking the impact of adverse childhood experiences on adult mental health. *Child Abuse & Neglect*, 69, 10–19.
- O’Neill, A., Stapley, E., Rehman, I., & Humphrey, N. (2023). Adolescent help-seeking: An exploration of associations with perceived cause of emotional distress. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 11, Article 1183092.
- Ojo, T. E., Akintola, A. A., & Animashaun, P. O. (2025). Assessment of adverse childhood experiences among in-school adolescents in Lagos State. *Corpus Intellect*, 4(2), 1–20.
- Ojo, T. E., Akintola, A. A., Ogunsemi, J. O., Sekoni, T. T., Adekoya, T. S., & Sama, B. O. (2024). Development and validation of Redeemer’s University adverse childhood experiences. *North American Journal of Psychology*, 26(4), 957–966.
- Petrucelli, K., Davis, J., & Berman, T. (2019). Adverse childhood experiences and associated health outcomes: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Child Abuse & Neglect*, 97, 104127. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chiabu.2019.104127>
- Priyam, P., & Nath, S. (2021). A cross-sectional study on the effect of adverse childhood events and perception toward parents on emotional intelligence. *Primary Care Companion for CNS Disorders*, 23(5), 20m02861. (
- Sacks, V., & Murphy, D. (2018). *The prevalence of adverse childhood experiences, nationally, by state, and by race or ethnicity*. Child Trends.
- Salawu, M. M., & Owoaje, E. (2020). Prevalence and predictors of adverse childhood experiences among youths in rural communities of Oyo State, Southwestern Nigeria. *Journal of Community Medicine and Primary Health Care*, 32(2), 27–41.
- Schutte, N. S., Malouff, J. M., Hall, L. E., Haggerty, D. J., Cooper, J. T., Golden, C. J., & Dornheim, L. (1998). Development and validation of a measure of emotional intelligence. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 25(2), 167–177.
- Shaiful Bahari, I., Norhayati, M. N., Nik Hazlina, N. H., Mohamad Shahirul Aiman, C. A. A., & Nik Muhammad Arif, N. A. (2021). Psychological impact of polygamous marriage on women and children: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth*, 21(1), 823. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12884-021-04301-7>
- Sidebotham, P., & Golding, J.; ALSPAC Study Team. (2001). Avon longitudinal study of parents and children—Child maltreatment in the children of the nineties: A longitudinal study of parental risk factors. *Child Abuse & Neglect*, 25(9), 1177–1200. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0145-2134\(01\)00261-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0145-2134(01)00261-7)
- Sidebotham, P., & Heron, J.; ALSPAC Study Team. (2006). Child maltreatment in the children of the nineties: A cohort study of risk factors. *Child Abuse & Neglect*, 30(5), 497–522. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chiabu.2005.11.005>
- Soares, A. L., Howe, L. D., Matijasevich, A., Wehrmeister, F. C., Menezes, A. M., & Gonçalves, H. (2016). Adverse childhood experiences: Prevalence and related factors in adolescents of a Brazilian birth cohort. *Child Abuse & Neglect*, 51, 21–30. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chiabu.2015.11.017>

Stith, S. M., Liu, T., Davies, L. C., Boykin, E. L., Alder, M. C., Harris, J. M., Som, A., McPherson, M., & Dees, J. E. M. E. G. (2009). Risk factors in child maltreatment: A meta-analytic review of the literature. *Aggression and Violent Behavior, 14*(1), 13–29.

Supke, M., Hahlweg, K., Schulz, W., & Job, A. K. (2025). Sex-specific differences in the experience of adverse childhood experiences: Transmission, protective, and risk factors from the perspectives of parents and their children — Results of an 18-year German longitudinal study. *Child and Adolescent Psychiatry and Mental Health, 19*(1), 46. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13034-025-00904-6>

Thornberry, T. P., Matsuda, M., Greenman, S. J., Augustyn, M. B., Henry, K. L., Smith, C. A., & Ireland, T. O. (2014). Adolescent risk factors for child maltreatment. *Child Abuse & Neglect, 38*(4), 706–722. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chiabu.2013.08.009>

Ugwu, J. I., Ibeagha, P. N., Apex-Apeh, C. O., Onyishi, C. N., Onyishi, A. B., & Onyishi, I. E. (2024). The moderating role of emotional intelligence on the association between adverse childhood experiences and conduct problems of adolescents. *Journal of Psychology in Africa, 34*(5), 564–572.

Waehrer, G. M., Miller, T. R., Silverio Marques, S. C., Oh, D. L., & Burke Harris, N. (2020). Disease burden of adverse childhood experiences across 14 states. *PLoS ONE, 15*, e0226134.

Witt, A., Brown, R. C., Plener, P. L., Brähler, E., & Fegert, J. M. (2017). Child maltreatment in Germany: Prevalence rates in the general population. *Child and Adolescent Psychiatry and Mental Health, 11*, 47. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13034-017-0185-0>

World Health Organization. (2020). *Violence against children*. WHO.

